

THE HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHER TRAINING IN THE EARLY SCHOOL EDUCATION ASPECT OF THE TURKISH EDUCATION SYSTEM.

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Abstract

The most important and basement subject of Turkish Education System is to carr you a good teacher training system. Because it is a necessity. Teacher training is as well as important in general education, it is important in preschool education that newly faormated/prepared and recently it is thought tot be added into basing educatin in our country. Teacher training system is one of the most important dimensions of education system. The teacher training programsa are developed by Higher Education Council (YÖK). Because of not considered to be appropriate to develope for only first time, it is necessary to develop such as a live and dynamic process by evaluating in application continuously.

In this study especially the proportion of content categories and formation that were necessary to be in the teacher training programmes were investigated in terms of teacher training programs for preschool education. This study was considered to be a screening model study and the quantitative differences were referred by studying on statistical data about teacher training and employment between definite time periods in preschool programs.

Key Words: *Preschool education programas, Preschool education, Preschool education teacher training programs.*

TÜRK EĞİTİM SİSTEMİNDE OKULÖNCESİ EĞİTİMİ BOYUTUYLA ÖĞRETMEN YETİŞTİRMENİN TARİHSEL GELİŞİMİ

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Özet

Eğitim sisteminin hedeflenen başarıya ulaşabilmesi için öğretmen yetiştirme sisteminin modern ve çağdaş bir anlayışla yapılandırılması gerekir. Okulöncesi eğitim kademesinde elde edilmesi gereken başarı açısından okul-aile işbirliği düşünüldüğünde, bunu sağlayabilecek donanımda öğretmenlere ihtiyaç olduğu açıktır. Dolayısıyla her toplum açısından öğretmen yetiştirme süreçleri eğitim sistemlerinin temel yapı taşıdır. Türkiye’de öğretmen yetiştirme programları Yüksek Öğretim Kurulu (YÖK) tarafından tasarlanır ve geliştirilir. Program geliştirme yaklaşım ve sistematığı çerçevesinde sürekli değiştirilmesinden ziyade programların uygulamada dirik süreçler olarak geliştirilmesi esası vardır.

Bu araştırmada özellikle öğretmen yetiştirme programlarının esasını teşkil eden içerik boyutların yapısı ve düzeni özellikle okulöncesi eğitimi öğretmen yetiştirme temelinde incelenmiştir incelenmiştir. Çalışma tarama modelli bir çalışma olup, okulöncesi eğitim programlarında belli zaman dilimleri arasında öğretmen yetiştirme ve istihdamı konusunda istatistiksel verilere bakılarak buradaki nicel farklılıklara değinilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: *Okulöncesi eğitim programları, okulöncesi eğitimi, okulöncesi öğretmeni yetiştirme programları.*

Introduction

The healthy, unified, and integrated continuation of social existence depends on the adoption and assimilation of national culture by young people, its development through their contributions, and its transformation into civilizational values that will contribute to all of humanity—a primary task of educational programs. In this context, the cultural development of young people is the most fundamental function of educational institutions. As confirmed by educational scientists, education is the process of intentionally creating a desired change in an individual's behavior based on their own life experiences and expertise. This process is a living and cyclical one with many variables. We can define behavioral change as the replacement of a previously acquired and undesirable behavior with a desirable one, the completion of a desired but incomplete behavior, and the acquisition of a desired behavior from scratch (Ertürk, 1976). Education is evaluated under two main headings: formal and informal processes. Informal education is concerned with learning acquired through chance and coincidence, without a plan or program. Formal processes, on the other hand, refer to planned applications with predetermined goals within a specific program framework. Informal learning refers to haphazard learning acquired within the family or social environment, among spouses, friends, and peer groups (Erden, 1998). Formal education processes can also be defined as formal and non-formal processes. It includes primary, secondary, and higher

education. Within these educational levels, preschool education, which provides educational services as an introduction to other educational levels, occupies a very important and critical place (Oğuzkan, 1981, p. 109). Preschool education is defined in the Dictionary of Educational Terms as: 1- Education conducted by families and various institutions from birth to the compulsory education age, taking into account the developmental characteristics, individual differences, and individual abilities and talents of children, with the aim of supporting their physical, emotional, and social development. 2- Education given to children of preschool age in nurseries, kindergartens, or preschool classes, focusing on the development of individual differences, the acquisition of social habits, and the development of problem-solving skills. 3- Aral, Kandır, and Yaşar (2001, p. 13) define preschool education as encompassing the period from birth to the age of primary education, covering ages 0-6. It is known to directly influence the physical, psychomotor, emotional, mental, and language development of children, which is crucial in later stages of life and development. Furthermore, basic personality structures are largely formed during this period. In short, it can be defined as the early childhood development period.

From another perspective, Yılmaz (2003, p. 12) states that preschool education is a systematic educational process that guides the basic developmental dimensions of children aged 0-72 months, particularly within the framework of societal culture, values, and norms; it enhances emotional development and perception capacity, assists in reasoning and logic, develops creativity, enables self-expression, and increases self-control. Therefore, it can be considered that preschool education enables children to socialize and provides them with the readiness levels and entry behaviors in terms of cognitive, affective, and motor skills for later educational stages. Preschool education gains even greater importance as it is the first step of education. A common feature that stands out in the definitions is that when preschool education is given in a planned, programmed, and appropriate environment during the 0-6 age developmental period, it establishes the basic parameters for both this period and subsequent developmental periods.

This process, which begins in the preschool period, is a gateway to education as it is the first step. It is a period of socialization where the child is separated from their family for the first time and interacts with different people. During this educational period, some role changes may occur based on interactions and relationships with different characters outside the family. The quality of education given in the preschool developmental period can be considered the most effective factor in the emotional and mental development of the child. High-quality education given in the preschool period is indispensable for developing the capacities that children are born with. Because when this process is carried out healthily, it ensures learning and willingness to learn, and facilitates their success throughout their lives (Kerem and Cömert, 2004).

Research conducted on preschool education indicates that the developments and achievements in this field during this period will significantly affect many abilities and competencies that children will develop in later developmental periods and educational stages. As Bloom (1964) attempted to demonstrate in his studies, it is known that 50% of an individual's mental development process up to the age of 17 is completed by the age of 4, 30% from age 4 to 8, and 20% from age 8 to 17. For this reason, there is a need for children to receive a better education and have their environment enriched during this period. However, a

very important problem arises here. Because the question of who should provide this education is essentially a significant source of problems that needs to be addressed. During this critical developmental period, it is necessary to guide the child in developing the abilities and skills they inherit at birth, to warn them about events in their environment, to monitor their actions and thoughts, and thus to reinforce correct behaviors. Meeting all these demands and expectations can only be achieved with a preschool teacher who has received good training in their field and teacher education.

The History and Current State of Preschool Education

When examining preschool education in Turkey as a historical process, it is necessary to analyze it under separate headings: before and after the proclamation of the Republic. This is because significant differences exist in the practices and programs implemented during these two periods.

Preschool Education in the Pre-Republican Period

When the historical processes of education and teaching practices in a society are examined, important clues can be obtained about the structure and functioning of other social institutions in that society. Therefore, the history of preschool education is also the history of social change and transformation. Political, economic, social, familial, religious, and health-related social events affecting society have directly affected everything related to children, and when this structure is considered as a cyclical process, how they influence each other becomes clear. In Turkey, the idea of raising children outside the family in specific institutions under the guidance of professional educators before reaching compulsory primary education age dates back to ancient times. The Sophists, described as the first technocrats of education and teaching, can be cited as an example of this. However, the systematic implementation of these and similar requirements and demands may not be considered very old. While not exactly like today, various educational institutions providing preschool education for children in this age range existed even before, according to various sources.

For example, during the Ottoman Empire, there were "Sibyan Schools," which can be described as primary education institutions within the context of the conditions of that era. It seems that efforts are still being made to keep these school structures active today (Akyüz (2007, pp. 88-80). The Ottomans, inheriting from the Seljuks and other Islamic countries, implemented primary education institutions called Mektep and Küttap. These educational institutions and structures are referred to in the Waqf deeds as Darüttalim, Mektep, Mektephane, Muallimhane, and Darülilim, but among the public they were called neighborhood schools or Sibyan Mektebi (primary school). These schools were found in almost every neighborhood and village. They were especially built near or adjacent to mosques. These schools were established primarily by statesmen or wealthier individuals and families through endowments. The expenses and needs of these structures were also met through endowments. On the other hand, if schools were built and the education process was run by the people in villages and neighborhoods through communal effort, then all the expenses of the school were covered by the parents and families. For example, Sultan

Mehmed the Conqueror... In his endowment deed, he stated that his school would accept orphans, but if no orphans could be found, then poorer children. Examining the historical process, Bayezid II also included similar statements in his own endowment deed, maintaining the same conditions. Children aged 5-6, both boys and girls, could attend the non-compulsory primary schools (Sibyan Mektepleri) in a neighborhood, and the education process could last 3-4 years.

The curriculum in these primary schools focused heavily on Quran recitation. The meaning of the Quran was not explained. At the same time, children were taught basic religious knowledge and practical religious practices, which were then put into practice. Generally speaking, the Mufti, Qadi, and the school's teacher were responsible for the administration and management of the school. In these primary schools, established through endowments, the founder also had certain duties and responsibilities (Akyüz, 2007).

At that time, most parents sent their children to these primary schools at a very young age. They also had the opportunity to send their children. In fact, the main purpose here was not so much for the child to learn anything in the name of education and instruction, but rather to ensure that the child sat quietly and quietly in the school, while providing a more comfortable environment for the mother at home (Akyüz, 1996, Oktay, 2004). There was no objection to these children being placed in a single room and made to sit in a corner in the primary school. Because these schools were single-roomed. In this respect, primary schools were partly similar to kindergartens, nurseries, and daycare centers (Akyüz, 1996).

It can be said that the orphanages (Darüleytam) opened in November 1914 during the time of Şükrü Bey, the Minister of Education at that time, functioned more like kindergartens. In some places, kindergarten classes were also established in the Darüleytams opened for girls, and boys and girls aged 2-7 were educated and protected in these schools. (Akyüz, 1996).

Looking at the historical process, before the Republican era, similar services were provided by the aforementioned primary schools, reformatories, and orphanages, as well as by governesses employed by wealthy families in the late Ottoman period (2005, p. 151).

The first serious steps in preschool education began during the Second Constitutional Period (1908-1918), and thus significant progress began in this field. These processes upon examination, it becomes clear that the primary schools were officially established between 1912 and 1913. This period coincides with the Balkan Wars. A thorough evaluation of the subsequent processes reveals numerous developments and transformations, but also highlights the undertaking of certain initiatives without adequate preparation. For example, it appears that there were no female teachers in these primary schools at that time. This indicates a failure to train female teachers. To compensate for this deficiency, efforts were made to recruit female teachers from other minority groups. In a sense, all aspects of the schooling were left to them. Furthermore, poems and songs for the students were written by these women (Akyüz et al., 2005; Akyüz, 2007).

Preschool Education in the Republican Era

In the pre-republican era, certain initiatives were taken to address general educational problems, and it appears that some efforts were made, particularly in the area of preschool

education. Within this framework, schools were opened to provide early childhood education. Legal regulations were also prepared for the management and administration of these schools, but these initiatives were insufficient. This is because the work undertaken in this area lacked continuity.

Looking at the post-republican era, immediately after the establishment of the Republic of Turkey, those working to overcome all the negative aspects of Turkish society in terms of social, cultural, political, and economic aspects within its institutional structures did not overlook the need to find human resources suitable for and capable of supporting this new structure, and they exerted intense effort in this regard. However, due to certain factors, preschool education could not be given priority (Duman, 1995).

When the Republic was declared by Gazi Mustafa Kemal Atatürk and his comrades, the conditions in the country necessitated prioritizing primary education above all else. However, it cannot be said that these educational institutions were at a level that could meet expectations and needs. In those early years, as described above, the Republic of Turkey was striving to create a new citizen profile. Therefore, as efforts were made to expand primary education starting in 1930, work on kindergartens was hampered, and a significant portion of the resources of these educational institutions were allocated to the development of primary education in general. Consequently, pre-school education was largely left to the responsibility of families and local administrations (Oktay, 2004; Aral et al., 2001).

Following the adoption of the law concerning primary education and education in general, regulatory work began to implement the provisions of the law. As a result of this work, the "Kindergarten Regulations" were published on June 16, 1962 (Öz, 1983). The National Education Basic Law No. 1739, which regulates Turkish National Education, was also adopted and put into effect in 1973. It should be noted that Article 19 of this law states: The definition of preschool education is given in Article 20; the aims and duties of preschool education are addressed in Article 21; and the opening, management, and administration of preschool education institutions are included in Article 21 (Ministry of National Education, 1993).

The Role and Importance of the Teacher in Preschool Education

The authority and responsibilities of families in preschool education are quite significant. "Early Childhood Education," as expressed by UNESCO, and commonly referred to as "Preschool Education" in Turkey, is, as in other countries, an educational stage/period largely under the responsibility of families. Its importance has steadily increased since the eighteenth century, moving beyond being solely the responsibility of families. At this point, the teacher becomes the key stakeholder in managing the process and assisting families.

Achieving the targeted success in preschool education undoubtedly depends on communication, interaction, and cooperation among the stakeholders in this process. At the same time, the qualifications and performance of the teacher, who is the main actor in this process, are also very important (Oğuzkan and Oral, 1983, p. 90). The sense of security the teacher instills in children is an indispensable parameter in the teacher's performance. From this perspective, children should not only be developed physically and cognitively, but also their affective domain values and emotional needs must be satisfied (Güler, 1994).

When we look at the studies conducted on what and to what extent teacher qualities should be within the framework of teacher training, it is understood that the focus is particularly on the qualities of an effective teacher. When the research on the subject is evaluated, it is seen that the essential competencies of an effective and competent teacher are grouped under eight main headings. These competencies can be listed as: primarily, top-level subject and professional knowledge, communication skills, general and local cultural knowledge, a spirit of amateurism along with professionalism, enthusiasm, sincerity, reliability, high expectations for achievement, support, cooperation, and flexibility (Demirel, 2007).

Preschool Teacher Training Efforts

It is known that towards the end of the 19th century in the Ottoman Empire, some minorities in the country opened their own kindergartens. As can be understood, the establishment of these and similar schools by Muslims was unfortunately very delayed. Before July 23, 1908, there were some attempts in this regard, and "Kindergartens" were opened in some provinces within the framework of state education. However, it is understood that a few private kindergartens were opened in Istanbul after this date. The establishment of official, state-run kindergartens only occurred after the Balkan Wars. During this period, many attempts were made regarding this field of education, but it cannot be said that sufficient preparation was achieved. For example, since female teachers were not trained for these schools, female teachers were obtained from minorities who had previously opened and operated their own kindergartens. It turned out that the methods and techniques they used were outdated methods abandoned by Europe. However, after a long time, the path of training female teachers was taken.

The most significant problem encountered in the opening and nationwide expansion of kindergartens was the inability to meet the need for fully trained and equipped teachers. As stated, these primary schools began to open with little preparation. When the need for teachers for kindergartens arose, we see that certain efforts were made by the state. In this context, between 1914-1915, a "Kindergarten Teacher Training School" was opened under the "Darülmualimat Program" within the Istanbul Darülmualimat. Thus, it is understood that the path to training kindergarten teachers in Turkey was taken. This school consisted of: 1. Primary School, 2. Darülmualimat-ı İbtidaiye Primary School, 3. Kindergarten Teacher Training School, and 4. Kindergarten School. The Kindergarten Teacher Training School had a one-year curriculum. The Kindergarten School was its practice school (Öztürk, 2005, 59).

The most significant problem encountered in the opening and expansion of kindergartens throughout the country was the inability to meet the need for fully trained and equipped teachers.

Problem Statement/Question

How have the processes of preschool teacher training and curriculum development taken place historically in Turkey?

Sub-Problems

1- Considering curriculum development efforts, what changes have been made to the number of preschool teacher training undergraduate programs?

a) What changes have been made to the number of Teacher Professional Knowledge, General Culture, and Elective courses?

b) What changes have been made to the hours and credits of Teacher Professional Knowledge courses?

c) What changes have been made to the hours and credits of Subject Matter courses?

Research Objective

This study aims to present the development efforts and changes made in preschool teacher training undergraduate programs from a historical perspective and to provide information about the curriculum changes that have occurred within the program framework. From this perspective, examining the changes made in the categories of Teacher Professional Knowledge, Subject Matter, and General Culture courses and determining the educational process that preschool teacher candidates undergo constitutes the main theme of this research. Thus, the goal is to contribute to the field.

Importance of the Research

Raising young people who have acquired healthy and desirable behaviors from psychological, social, and cultural perspectives, maximizing the inherited values they bring with them at birth, supporting their healthy developmental characteristics, and providing them with appropriate educational and training environments within this framework are the most fundamental expectations of today's teachers. Therefore, having teachers who meet these qualities should be the primary justification. Scientific studies aimed at evaluating the current state of teacher training within the framework of a differences approach, assessing past practices with their desired or undesirable results, and designing and implementing new and more excellent educational programs are of vital importance.

Limitations

This study is limited to a historical perspective on teacher training, and specifically to preschool teacher training programs and related curriculum changes.

Research Methodology

Research methodology can be defined as the arrangement of necessary resources and opportunities for the collection and analysis of data in a way that is appropriate to the purpose of the research and sustainable and capable of achieving its goals. This research is a qualitative study structured through documentary research based on a survey model (Seltiz, Jahoda, Deutsch and Cook, 1959: cited in Karasar, 2007).

In fact, the survey model is a research approach that aims to describe a situation or problem that existed in the past or present, in its existing form and state (Karasar, 2007). On the other hand, it describes the concrete situation, individual, or object that is the subject of the research and experienced firsthand, within its own conditions, that is, as it is. Similarly, documentary research can be defined as collecting data by examining and evaluating existing records and documents. As can be understood, one can be expressed as general survey, and the other as content analysis.

From these perspectives, this study was conducted to determine the historical process of teacher training practices for preschool education in our country, and the changes and adjustments made to the curriculum of university preschool education programs. Therefore, content analysis was carried out within the framework of a documentary research model.

Findings and Interpretation

The answers obtained in the context of the problem question and sub-problem questions determined for the research are as follows:

1- How have the processes of training preschool teachers and developing programs historically unfolded in Turkey?

It is known that towards the end of the 19th century in the Ottoman Empire, some minorities in the country opened their own kindergartens. As can be understood, the establishment of these and similar schools by Muslims was unfortunately very delayed. Before July 23, 1908, there were some attempts in this regard, and "Kindergartens" were opened in some provinces within the framework of state education. However, it is understood that a few private kindergartens were opened in Istanbul after this date. The establishment of official, state-run kindergartens only occurred after the Balkan Wars. During this period, many attempts were made regarding this field of education, but it cannot be said that sufficient preparation was achieved. For example, since female teachers were not trained for these schools, female teachers were recruited from minorities who had previously opened and operated their own kindergartens. It turned out that the methods and techniques they used were outdated methods abandoned by Europe. However, after a long time, the path of training female teachers was taken.

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The pre-school teacher training undergraduate programs included:

1. What changes have been made to the number of Teacher Professional Knowledge, Subject Area Knowledge, General Culture, and elective courses?

a) What changes have been made to the number of Teacher Professional Knowledge, General Culture, and elective courses?

b) What changes have been made to the hours and credits of Teacher Professional Knowledge courses?

c) What changes have been made to the hours and credits of Subject Area Knowledge courses?

The courses offered within the framework of the undergraduate programs for teacher training in preschool education consist of Teacher Professional Knowledge, Subject Area Knowledge, General Culture, and Elective Courses.

Data regarding the number of courses and their percentage ratios in the program are given in Table-1.

Table-1 Preschool Education Program Curriculum Distribution in the Past and Present

Courses	Previous Undergraduate Program		Current New Undergraduate Program	
	n	%	n	%
Professional Knowledge	9	17,7	13	21
Field Knowledge	31	60,8	28	45
General Knowledge	7	13,7	16	26
Elective	4	7,8	5	8
Total	51	100	62	100

(MEB)

When examining the data in Table 1, it is seen that 4 additional "Professional Knowledge" courses have been added to the new undergraduate program training teachers for preschool education. This indicates a 3.3% increase in the weight of "Professional Knowledge" courses in the new program.

Regarding "Field Knowledge" courses, it appears that 3 courses have been removed from the program. This represents a 15.8% reduction in the number of courses in the new program.

In terms of General Culture courses, there has been an increase of 9 courses. This increase represents a 12.3% increase in the program.

Regarding elective courses, it appears that one additional course has been added to the new program. However, when looking at the new undergraduate program as of 2016, excluding the starred electives, 5 elective courses have been added. This represents a 0.2% increase in weight (Higher Education Council, 1998, p. 11).

Table 1 shows the distribution of courses in the undergraduate programs for preschool teacher training. In the new program, subject matter courses rank first with 45%, followed by general culture courses with 26%, and professional teaching knowledge courses with 21%.

Conclusion

Based on the research findings, the following conclusions can be drawn: Compared to the old curriculum, there is an increase in the number of subjects in the new curriculum, especially excluding "Subject Matter Knowledge" courses. From this perspective, the slight reduction in "Subject Matter Knowledge" courses might be considered a disadvantage for preschool teachers. However, if there is an equivalent in one or more of the other courses, it will not be a disadvantage; on the contrary, it will save teacher candidates more time and provide additional study opportunities for all subjects. However, if the reduction in courses was carried out without very objective measurement and evaluation, it may create problems due to insufficient information.

In the new program, it has been observed that the number of practical, theoretical, and total hours, as well as the credit hours, of "Teacher Professional Knowledge" courses have been increased. This should be considered quite important and positive when considering the competencies of the teaching profession. Considering the problems experienced in the teacher training system and practices in our country and in the practice of the profession, this can be said to be quite significant. On the other hand, it has been observed that the number of practical, theoretical, and total hours, as well as the credit hours, of "General Culture" courses have also been increased. In the new program, in terms of the number of theoretical class hours, "Field Knowledge" courses have a significant weight, followed by "General Culture and Professional Knowledge" courses.

Suggestions

The number of practical application hours in the curriculum of the undergraduate program for preschool education teachers should definitely be increased. Increasing the number of internship hours (per semester) to at least four semesters would be professionally beneficial. It appears that this is the rationale behind the increase in course hours, as it must be accepted that theoretical knowledge can be applied to real life through school practices. Particular attention should also be paid to ensuring coordination and a balanced distribution of courses across all areas within the undergraduate program for preschool education teachers.

It is recommended that instead of making additions or removals to courses related to the four core areas identified for future development work in the preschool education program without scientific justification, courses should be developed based on scientific principles and considering the examples of developed countries in terms of their level of success in solving educational problems.

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